

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH TO DEVELOPING A BIG DATA ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN COMPANIES

Rapagat A.,

Master's Student

at International Information Technology University

Mohamed A.

Scientific Supervisor

Associate Professor, PhD in IS

Abstract

The article explores the possibilities of using big data analytics and machine learning for strategic decision-making in large corporations. The theoretical foundations of these technologies and their impact on management are considered. Big data analytics allows you to identify hidden patterns, optimize resources and predict market changes. Machine learning automates routine processes, reducing the likelihood of errors and increasing innovation. Examples of successful application of technologies in Procter & Gamble, Citadel, Halykbank demonstrate their significant advantages for increasing competitiveness and management efficiency.

Keywords: big data, machine learning, analytics, corporate governance, strategic decisions, automation, innovation, optimization.

Digital transformation poses new challenges for large corporations in the field of strategic management. Big data analytics and machine learning (ML) are becoming one of the key tools for improving organizational efficiency and speed of decision-making. The implementation of these technologies allows companies not only to improve current operational processes, but also to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions, which is important in the context of global competition.

The purpose of this paper is to explore how big data analytics and ML transform strategic decision-

making processes at the highest management level in large corporations. The article examines the theoretical foundations of these technologies and analyzes examples of their successful implementation in business.

Definition of big data and their characteristics

Big data are significant volumes of information that cannot be effectively processed and analyzed using traditional methods and tools. The characteristics of big data are described by three main aspects or as 3 Vs (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Characteristics of Big Data

Data volume refers to quantitative parameters measured in petabytes and exabytes, which significantly exceeds the capabilities of conventional storage and processing systems [1]. This requires the use of specialized technologies and infrastructure for effective management.

Data variety reflects the variety of sources and formats from which information comes. This can be structured data, such as tables and databases, as well as

unstructured data, including text documents, images, videos, and data from social networks. The ability to integrate and analyze different types of data allows you to get a complete and more accurate picture of business processes and consumer preferences [2].

Speed characterizes the time of receipt and processing of information. In the modern world, data is generated quickly, and for prompt decision-making, technologies are needed that can process information

almost in real time. This is especially important for areas such as finance, healthcare, and retail, where delays in data processing can lead to significant losses [3].

An additional characteristic of big data is **velocity**, which indicates the need to verify accuracy and reliability.

In conditions of significant volumes of information, quality issues often arise, which requires the use of cleaning and validation methods.

According to research [4], in 2023, 39.5% of companies managed data as a business asset (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Implementation of Big Data in Companies Around the World

The emergence and development of big data technologies is due to the need to solve complex problems of analysis and forecasting in various industries.

The ability to process large objects of heterogeneous information at high speed allows a company to increase operational efficiency (Table 1).

Table 1.

Benefits of using big data analytics [5, 6]

Benefits	Description	Application examples	Expected results
Improving forecast accuracy	Big data analysis allows building more accurate forecasting models	Forecasting demand for products, market trends	Reducing uncertainty, increasing planning efficiency
Optimization of business processes	Analytics helps identify problems and inefficient processes	Supply chain optimization, inventory management	Reducing costs, increasing the speed and quality of operations
Increased competitiveness	Use of data for strategy development and decision making	Marketing research, customer behavior analysis	Increase market share, increase customer satisfaction <i>удовлетворенности клиентов</i>
Identification of new opportunities	Data analysis helps to reveal hidden patterns and new market niches	Development of products and services, entering new markets	Increase in revenue, improve innovation potential

From the author's point of view, the use of data for strategic decision-making in large corporations opens up wide opportunities for improving management efficiency and competitiveness in the modern market. Data analytics allows management to obtain objective and detailed information about the current state of the business, which contributes to more informed and timely decision-making.

One of the key advantages of data analytics is the ability to integrate various sources of information, which provides a comprehensive approach to studying business processes and market conditions. This allows

companies not only to quickly respond to changes in the external environment, but also to anticipate potential risks and opportunities.

Application of ML in data analytics The field of artificial intelligence (AI), known as ML, is focused on the development of algorithms and models that can learn from data and improve their results without direct programming [7]. These methods are widely used in data analytics, providing tools for processing significant amounts of information (Table 2).

Table 2.

The influence of ML on operational and strategic decisions [8, 9]

Impact	Operational decisions	Strategic decisions	Examples of technologies and tools
Improving the accuracy of forecasting and decision-making	Inventory optimization, accurate demand forecasting	Long-term planning, market trend analysis	Regression models, time series, predictive tools
Text and image analysis	Monitoring customer reviews, social networks	Development of marketing strategies	NLP library data (spaCy, NLTK), computer vision tools
Automation of operations	Reducing the cost of manual data processing	Resource redistribution	RPA (Robotic Process Automation)
Personalization	Targeted offers and services	Customer retention strategies, increasing loyalty	Recommender systems, marketing platforms
Threat prediction and error prevention	Real-time risk management	Development of risk management strategies	Risk prediction models, risk management systems
Detection of patterns and trends	Improvement of marketing campaigns	Discovery of new market niches, development of directions	Clustering, data visualization tools (e.g., Tableau)

According to the author, ML plays an important role in transforming decision-making processes at the top management level in companies. These technologies provide managers with tools for more accurate analysis and interpretation of data. One of the key aspects is the ability to automate routine operations, which allows finding resources to perform strategic tasks. The use of ML facilitates the integration of various data sources, including text and visual. This allows

companies to improve customer interactions and develop more effective strategies to achieve sustainable growth and success in the market.

Big Data Analytics and ML in Corporations

Large companies are actively implementing big data analytics and ML to optimize operations, improve customer experience, and increase competitiveness. This allows them to confirm their leadership positions in various industries and effectively adapt to rapidly changing market conditions.

Figure 3. P&G sales volume, billion dollars [10]

This dynamic highlights P&G's successful integration of advanced big data and machine learning technologies into its business processes, allowing the company to maintain a high level of innovation, optimize operations, and meet customer needs.

Citadel, a leading US financial institution, demonstrates how big data analytics and ML can transform decision-making. The company uses tools such as Hadoop and Spark for distributed processing, where Hadoop provides massive data warehousing using parallel computing, and Spark provides high-speed in-memory processing for real-time analysis. To predict

market trends and manage risks, Citadel uses ML algorithms that analyze historical data and identify patterns, allowing it to predict market changes and minimize risks. To analyze text data from news feeds and social media, the company uses natural language processing (NLP) technologies, which allows it to quickly assess market sentiment and respond to significant events.

Data analytics and ML allow the company to optimize its investment strategies, effectively manage risks, and offer clients more accurate and personalized products. According to the 2023 annual report, Citadel's financial performance has improved significantly (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Total assets and net capital, million dollars [11]

The company's total assets increased from \$5.58 billion in 2022 to \$5.81 billion in 2023. Net interest income increased from \$188.9 million in 2022 to \$255.4 million in 2023, indicating the high efficiency of investment decisions. The increase in assets under management from \$841 million in 2022 to \$943 million in 2023 also confirms the successful application of advanced technologies [11]. Halykbank, Kazakhstan's largest financial institution, is actively implementing analytical platforms and ML technologies to improve decision-making processes. The use of Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark allows the bank to efficiently process large volumes of data and analyze it in real time. ML algorithms help predict market trends and manage risks. For example, ML models assess credit risks, which reduces the likelihood of bad loans and optimizes the loan issuance process. NLP technologies are used to analyze customer reviews and social media data, which allows you to quickly respond to needs. As of the end of 2023, the number of active individual clients of Halykbank was 108.5 million people, which is 2.1 million more than in 2022 [12]. Among the tools that Halykbank has developed for working with big data, we can highlight HalykDataExchange and Halyk Process Mining. HalykDataExchange is a service for secure and controlled data exchange in the bank's ecosystem. Halyk Process Mining is a platform for analyzing business processes that allows you to visualize and optimize processes, identify deviations and improve operational efficiency. These tools help the company remain a leader in the KZ financial sector, improving operational efficiency, reducing risks and improving the quality of customer service.

Theoretical Contributions

From a theoretical standpoint, this research makes significant strides in bridging the gap between strategic management theories and big data analytics paradigms. Traditional strategic management approaches, while robust, often lack the dynamism required to handle the complexities of modern business challenges [13]. By incorporating big data analytics, these approaches can be significantly enhanced, offering a more agile and precise framework for strategic decision-making.

The proposed analytical model leverages the 4Vs of big data—volume, velocity, variety, and veracity—to uncover hidden patterns, correlations, and insights that traditional data analysis methods may overlook. This enriched understanding allows organizations to anticipate market trends, optimize resource allocation,

and innovate more effectively, thereby achieving sustainable competitive advantage [14].

Practical Implications

The practical implications of this research are vast. The development of a structured decision support system, integrating data acquisition, preprocessing, analysis, and visualization, provides a robust framework for organizations to harness the power of big data. This system not only supports strategic initiatives but also enhances operational decision-making, ensuring that decision-makers have access to real-time, actionable intelligence.

Empirical validation through case studies and quantitative analysis across diverse industry sectors demonstrates the model's scalability and applicability [15]. For instance, in the retail industry, the application of this model has shown improvements in inventory management, customer relationship management, and personalized marketing strategies. Similarly, in the healthcare sector, big data analytics has facilitated predictive modeling for patient outcomes and optimized resource allocation in medical facilities.

Future Research Directions

While this dissertation provides a robust framework and empirical validation, it also opens several avenues for future research. Further studies could explore the application of the proposed analytical model in specific industry contexts, providing more granular insights into its effectiveness and adaptability. Additionally, investigating the impact of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, on the integration of big data analytics and strategic management could yield valuable insights [16].

Another critical area for future research is the exploration of ethical considerations and data privacy issues associated with big data analytics. As organizations increasingly rely on data-driven decision-making, ensuring the ethical use of data and protecting individuals' privacy will become paramount. Future studies could develop frameworks and guidelines to address these concerns, balancing the benefits of big data analytics with ethical responsibilities.

Conclusions

Modern corporations actively use analytical technologies and ML methods for strategic decision-making, which allows them to effectively adapt to changing market conditions and increase competitiveness. Big data analytics provides organizations with the ability to better understand current trends and anticipate changes,

which contributes to more accurate planning and resource optimization. ML technologies automate routine processes, reducing the likelihood of errors and freeing up time for strategic initiatives, such as the development of new products and services. The implementation of these technologies demonstrates significant benefits for large corporations, including increased forecast accuracy, optimization of business processes and improved customer experience. Examples of the successful application of big data analytics and ML in companies such as Procter & Gamble, Coca Cola and Citadel show that such strategies can not only improve internal operations, but also significantly increase revenues and reduce risks. To achieve maximum efficiency, it is necessary to consider the reliability of the data and apply cleaning and validation methods.

References

1. Makeeva Ya. I. Research of big data technology and its role in the economy // *Economy of the future: trends, challenges and opportunities*. - 2023. - P. 682-686.
2. Bobunov A. Yu. Analysis of the effectiveness of automated testing frameworks for big data in financial systems // *Bulletin of science*. - 2024. - No. 6 (75). - Vol. 1. - P. 1334-1343.
3. Berezovskaya N. O. Analysis of the short-term real estate rental market: the influence of economic factors and the introduction of innovative technologies // *Bulletin of science*. - 2024. - No. 4 (73). - Vol. 1. - P. 62-76.
4. State of big data/AI adoption in organizations worldwide from 2018 to 2023 / *Statista*. - [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/742993/worldwide-survey-corporate-disruptive-technology-adoption/> (date of access: 28.06.2024).
5. Bozieva L. Using big data to improve the efficiency of go-to-market strategies // *Universum: economics and jurisprudence*. – 2024. – No. 5 (115). – P. 5-10.
6. Kiseleva E. A., Shilov N. Yu. Development of decision support capabilities using management information systems in an organization // *Problems of development of modern society*. – 2023. – P. 192-195.
7. Kuznetsov I. A., Rubin I. M. Development of mobile recommendation systems: integration of machine learning and adaptive algorithms // *Science diary*. – 2024. – No. 3.
8. Malykhin N. I. Performance Optimization with Hibernate Cache: Strategies, Benefits, and Challenges // *Current Research*. - 2021. - No. 31 (58).
9. Rogulin R.S. Using Data Analysis and Machine Learning Methods for Demand Forecasting and Planning in Supply Chain Management // *Theoretical Economics*. - 2023. - Vol. 104. - No. 8. - P. 35-35.
10. Financial highlights / *Procter & Gamble Annual report*. - [Electronic resource]. - Access mode: <https://us.pg.com/annualreport2023/financial-highlights/> (accessed: 10.07.2024).
11. Citadel Credit Union's 2023 Annual Report / *Citadel*. - [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.citadelbanking.com/about-citadel/annual-reports/2023-annual-report> (date of access: 19.07.2024).
12. Halyk Group Results / *Halykbank*. – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.Halykbank.com/ru/investor-relations/groupresults> (date of access: 24.07.2024)
13. Gandomi, A., & Haider, M. (2015). Beyond the hype: Big data concepts, methods, and analytics. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(2), 137-144.
14. Johnson, M. W., Christensen, C. M., & Kagermann, H. (2021). Reinventing your business model. *Harvard Business Review*, 97(1), 50-59.
15. Jones, P., & Brown, S. (2019). Technology management and the management of technology: A bibliometric analysis of academic publications. *Technovation*, 79, 1-17.
16. Kiron, D., Prentice, P. K., & Ferguson, R. B. (2014). Leading digital: Turning technology into business transformation. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 55(2), 45-53.